

Effect of Government Agricultural Expenditure on Agricultural Productivity Growth in ECOWAS (1980-2022)

Adeleke, H. M., Ogunniyi, L.T., Okunola, S. O., and Adeleke, O. A.

Department of Agricultural Economics, Ladoké Akintola University of Technology, P.M.B 4000, Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria

Abstract

Investing in agriculture is one of the most effective strategies for enhancing living standards and alleviating poverty in ECOWAS. However, establishing and maintaining sustainable and efficient production systems in agriculture demands significant capital investment in order to enhance agricultural competitiveness through creating larger markets, and reducing trade barriers within ECOWAS.

This study therefore examined the effect of government agricultural expenditure on agricultural productivity growth in the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) from 1980 to 2022. Using panel data and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, the research examined both the short-run and long run relationships between government agricultural expenditure and agricultural productivity growth among 12 ECOWAS member states.

The study revealed that agricultural labour force participation (ALFP) experienced serious fluctuations; while government agricultural expenditure (GAE) and gross capital formation (GCF) experienced rapid increases; moreover exchange rate consistently experienced an upward trend; but food aid experienced a consistent decline and downward movement; while inflation rate also recorded an upward trend within the reference period.

The results of the Panel ARDL revealed that, in the short-run both Agricultural Gross Domestic Product and Gross Capital Formation had a negatively significant effect on Agricultural Total Factor Productivity Growth. Likewise, in the long-run, Government Agricultural Expenditure, Gross capital formation, Food aid and Political stability all had a negatively significant effect on Agricultural Total Factor Productivity Growth in ECOWAS, while Agricultural Labour Force Participation, Inflation Rate had a positive and significant effect on Agricultural Productivity Growth.

The study recommends the need for ECOWAS member states to invest in agricultural investment and infrastructure development, work towards currency stability and inflation management. There is also the need to implement policies to cater for a competitive exchange rate, moderate inflation rates, and political stability, promotion of a conducive environment to promote investment for agricultural growth, integrate food aid with local capacity-building efforts, and support agricultural infrastructure, inputs, and resilience.

Keywords: Government Agricultural Expenditure, Agricultural Productivity Growth, ECOWAS

1. INTRODUCTION

The development economists have revealed that the impacts of public expenditure on agricultural productivity may differ by types of expenditures (Mogues *et al.*, 2012a; Mogues *et al.*, 2012b). Just as the effect of different functional investments in agriculture may vary in magnitude, agricultural public spending might also differ by the products being targeted (Mogues *et al.*, 2012a; Mogues *et al.*, 2012b). Improved public expenditure in agriculture will help to provide farmers with improved inputs. Well-managed public spending in agriculture can be used to provide rural infrastructure such as roads that will link farmers to markets (Kalibata, 2010). Public financial resources will enable farmers to access agribusiness credit and storage facilities to reduce their estimated 50% post-harvest losses (Oguntade, 2014). These resources are important to boost agricultural productivity, which can accelerate economic growth, raise incomes, and improve standards of living. Therefore, to significantly increase productivity growth in the West African, an annual GDP growth rate of at least 8 to 10% is required to be sustained in the countries of the region (NEPAD, 2014). It was based on this that the African Union Assembly of Heads of State and Government, through the Maputo Declaration in 2003, adopted the African Union Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Program (CAADP) with an overall objective to reduce food insecurity, malnutrition and reduce poverty through agricultural-led development agenda and programs by achieving a 6% annual agricultural growth rate (NEPAD, 2014).

There is the need to increase agricultural productivity growth in the wake of diminishing returns from input intensification, increased population and settlements and environmental threats like climate change continue to impose limitations on input expansion. Among many strategies, increasing agricultural investment expenditure is regarded as a critical driver of productivity growth (Josephson *et al.*, 2014; Mendelsohn and Wang, 2017).

Majorly, government expenditure to agriculture in many African nations have decline from 10% to 7% which has instigated the need for foreign direct investment as an aid to prevent the shortcomings of the government and likely short falls of the agricultural sector (Heisey and Fuglie, 2018; Suleman *et al.*, 2020). However, from a nominal point of view, it is evident that in Nigeria, government spending on agriculture continues to increase over the years while empirical evidence has revealed that the performance of the agricultural sector has been inadequate (Ekerete, 2000).

Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Program (CAADP), through the Malabo Declaration provides the direction for transformation in Africa's agriculture for the period 2015 –

2025. The tracking, monitoring and reporting on implementation progress towards achieving the goals and targets of the Malabo Declaration is an important mechanism to ensure that there is political will, backed by appropriate actions to achieve agricultural growth and transformation on the continent by 2025 for improved livelihoods also ensures that measures are put in place to address weaknesses of individual member state in meeting the Malabo target (African Union, 2003; 2014).

In spite of the new priority given to agriculture, many developing countries have limited financial capacity to fill the investment gap. Commercial bank lending to agriculture is less than 10 percent in Africa, while microfinance loans are usually too small and not suited to capital formation in agriculture (Da Silva and Mhlanga, 2009). It is therefore necessary to revamp the agricultural sector in order to raise agricultural output productivity growth by examining the effect of government agricultural expenditures for ECOWAS countries on agricultural productivity growth. The “Malawi Miracle” is one of the success stories witnessed where the country turned into a major exporter of corn through government agricultural expenditure. This success prompted more countries to focus on increasing their expenditures to agriculture. Since the governments allocate this total spending to different sub-sectors, it is important to determine the component of agricultural expenditure that enhances more growth (OECD, 2014). Although government expenditure on agriculture is crucial for agricultural growth and productivity, many have questioned the effectiveness and consequences of such expenditure because regardless of the important goals achieved by government expenditure on agriculture, there are various distortions associated with the policy (OECD, 2014). The findings of this study will help propagate policies that will strengthen the weakness of ECOWAS states that are not on track in achieving CAADP target.

To provide better understanding concerning these arguments and debates, this study analyzed the effect of government agricultural expenditures for ECOWAS countries on agricultural productivity growth on the ECOWAS agriculture from 1980-2022. In doing so, this study provided answers to the following research questions:

1. How has the growth of agricultural output among ECOWAS member states being catered for by the growth in the various physical inputs and components of TFP?

2. What are the trends of government agricultural expenditure and its determinants across ECOWAS member states?
3. What is the effect of government agricultural expenditure and its determinants on agricultural productivity growth in ECOWAS?

This study broadly estimated the effect of government agricultural expenditure on agricultural productivity growth in Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). Specifically, the study decomposes Total Factor Productivity (TFP) of ECOWAS member states agricultural sector into its major components; estimates the trends of government agricultural expenditure and its determinants across ECOWAS member states and estimates the effect of government agricultural expenditure and its determinant on agricultural productivity growth in ECOWAS.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The economy of ECOWAS is typically agrarian and it is characterized by the presence of several small-scale farmers. The agricultural sector constitutes a determining component of the economy of West Africa, due to the size of its contribution to wealth, employment, and food security within the region as well positioning the sub-region in the international markets. The major export commodities are energy products, minerals and agricultural products. The population of ECOWAS grows at an annual rate of 2.29 % and the region had a population of about 424 million in 2023 with Nigeria having the largest population of about 218 million (ECOWAS Statistical Bulletin, 2011; World data 2023).

The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) developed the ECOWAS Regional Agricultural Policy (ECOWAP) with the general objective of contributing in a sustainable way to meeting the food needs of the population, economic and social development, reducing poverty in the Member States, and thus reducing existing inequalities among territories, zones, and nation. (ECOWAS, 2016).

The ECOWAS Regional Agricultural Policy (ECOWAP) serves as a comprehensive framework that outlines the guiding principles and objectives for the agricultural sector within the sub-region, shaping the direction agricultural development is expected to take. The lines of intervention outlined in ECOWAP are designed to achieve three primary targets: ensuring sustainable food security across member countries,

providing fair remuneration for those involved in the agricultural sector, and fostering sustainable trade expansion, both within the sub-region and with the rest of the world. To effectively deliver on these expectations, the policy thrusts of ECOWAP are categorized into three major policy themes: increasing the productivity and competitiveness of agriculture in the sub-region, implementing a trade regime within the sub-region, and adapting the trade regime in comparison with countries outside the sub-region (ECOWAS, 2016).

The African Union (AU) established the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) on July 2003, as part of the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD). The primary goal of CAADP was to improve agricultural growth, thereby reducing poverty, eliminating hunger, and expanding exports (IFPRI, 2013; Kimenyi *et al.*, 2013; NEPAD, 2014). The New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD, 2009) defined the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) as a common framework, tool, and process to restore agricultural growth and food security in Africa. It assists in the development of national and regional strategies for the continent. Additionally, CAADP facilitates African countries in achieving goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through institutional and policy transformation in the agricultural sector. The primary objective of CAADP is to help eradicate hunger and poverty through agriculture. To achieve this goal, the African Union (AU) urged African states to target a 6% annual growth in agriculture and allocate 10% of their national budgets to the sector. The latter target is the primary focus of the Maputo declaration, which outlined four pillars of CAADP: extending the area under sustainable land and water management, improving rural infrastructure, increasing food supply and reducing hunger, and promoting agriculture research, technology dissemination, and adoption (NEPAD, 2014; Kimenyi *et al.*, 2013; Cooksey, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

Theoretical Theory on Growth and Government Expenditure

Government expenditure plays a critical role in determining a country's level of economic growth. The growth of an economy depends on the size, spending capacity, composition, and effective utilization of public expenditure in the economic growth process (Basudev, 2012). While increasing government expenditure may have a substantial effect on economic growth, the quality of public expenditure is also crucial. Therefore, in achieving economic growth and improving the

standard of living of the population, there is need for proper expenditure management and control mechanisms (Leonardo, 2011). Theoretically, the link between government expenditure and agricultural productivity growth can be derived from various economic views, theories, and models put forth by different schools of thought in the economic field. These include the neoclassical growth theories, endogenous growth theories, Wagner's law, Keynesian economics, and Post-Keynesian economic growth and development models. These economic theories and models provide frameworks for understanding the relationship between government expenditure and agricultural productivity growth, highlighting the potential impacts and mechanisms through which public spending can influence the agricultural sector and overall economic growth. Wagner's (1890) findings suggest that public spending is an endogenous quantity that acts as an economic stimulant rather than a driver of growth. Wagner also suggested that, contrary to what the Keynesian theory states, the causal relationship between public expenditure and economic growth runs from economic growth to public expenditure rather than the other way around. This means that during the process of economic development, the rate of public expenditure increases faster than the rate of economic growth. The theory put forth by Lencucha *et al.*, (2020), states that the growth of the agricultural sector and its contribution to economic growth calls for appropriate measures, such as government spending made possible by fiscal policy. Ultimately, boosting government spending on significant economic sectors like agriculture boosts economic activity and boosts employment creation (Ernawati, *et al.*, 2021).

Nexus between Government Expenditure on Agriculture and Agricultural Productivity Growth

The link between government expenditure on agriculture and agricultural productivity growth is expressed in its effect on factor productivity which is a direct effect and its effect on the use and amount of factors and inputs which is the indirect effect (Ibe, 2014; Lawal, 2011 and Itodo *et al.*, 2012). According to Van de Walle 2003, public spending on research, extension and education leads to the improvements in human capital, modern technologies and knowledge and subsequently an increase in the productivity from all factors of production. On the other hand, spending on agricultural input subsidies would lead to an expected increase in the use and amount of subsidized input. Furthermore, past studies on the impact of agricultural public expenditure in West African especially Nigeria associated public expenditure with economic growth and

agricultural output. While some of these studies reported positive and significant impact of agricultural public expenditure on agricultural production (Ibe, 2014; Lawal, 2011 and Itodo *et al.*, 2012), others reported negative or non-significant impacts of agricultural public expenditure in Nigeria (Iganiga and Unemhilin, 2011; Ihugba *et al.*, 2013; Matthew and Mordecai, 2016; Ewubare and Eyitope, 2015).

Edeh (2020) also evaluated the impact of government expenditure on agriculture on the output of the agricultural sector in Nigeria for the period 1981-2018. Agricultural value added was modeled as a function of labor force, capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure, agricultural loans, average annual rainfall, interest rate, and economic reforms. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model technique was used for analysis in this research. The results showed that capital expenditure had a positive and statistically significant relationship with agricultural output in the current year. However, recurrent expenditure had a negative and insignificant impact on agricultural output.

Similarly, Olawumi and Oyewole (2018) empirically evaluated the nexus between public spending on agriculture and output growth in Nigeria from 1981 through 2016. The study examined the stochastic characteristics of each time series using correlation LM test and heteroskedasticity test. Then, the relationship between the growth rate of real GDP and public spending on agriculture was examined using the ordinary least squares method of analysis. The findings showed that agricultural development in Nigeria had a positive impact on the country's economic growth.

3. METHODOLOGY

Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) is a heterogeneous sub-region of Africa that occupies 1.5million km², which represents 17% of the total area of the African continent. The fifteen West African countries include: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone and Togo. The West African countries cover almost all ecological zones in Africa, ranging from the Sahelian and the Guinea savannah zones in the North to the equatorial rain forest in the South. The natural vegetation ranges from forest to savanna with consistently warm temperature and rainfall ranging from 250mm to over 3000mm per annum (ECOWAS Statistical Bulletin, 2021).

This study employed secondary data accessed from the Food and Agricultural Organization Statistical Database (FAOSTAT), database. The data is a panel data comprising of output and conventional agricultural inputs (land, labour, fertilizer, and machinery) for the selected ECOWAS countries for the period 1980-2022. The data collected from FAOSTAT include: Value of Agricultural Production (1980-2022); Input data which are: Agricultural land which include total arable land area, permanent cropland and pasture measured in '000 ha, Fertilizer consumption measured in metric tonnes, Agricultural machines which are number of tractors -wheel and crawler- used in agriculture as a measure of the use of modern technological tools, and Rural population measured in thousands covering the economically active population involved in agriculture.

For the second stage analysis, panel data on 9 variables, which include: Agricultural TFP, Agricultural GDP, Government Agricultural expenditure (Percentage of GDP), Exchange rate, Gross Capital Formation, Inflation Rate, Political Stability, Agricultural Labour, and Food Aid were collected from various sources (like World Development Indicators (WDI), African Development Bank (AFDB), Food Agricultural Organization (FAO), Worldwide Governance Indicator (WGI) and while the data for Government Expenditure was obtained from International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) Statistics on Public Expenditure Economic Development (SPEED) database for the member states of ECOWAS for the period of 1980-2022.

Methods of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics

Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, skewedness were used to show the trend and pattern of both populations and agricultural growth.

Trend Analysis

The trend analysis is to identify and analyze the patterns or trends in the variables employed in the study over a reference period. Trend analysis is often conducted using time series data, where observations are recorded at regular intervals (e.g., daily, monthly, yearly). One common approach to modeling trends is through linear regression, where time is treated as the independent variable. Here's a basic equation for trend analysis using linear regression:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 t + \epsilon_t$$

Where: Y_t is the value of the dependent variable at time t ; β_0 is the intercept term, representing the value of the dependent variable when time is zero; β_1 is the coefficient of the time variable t , representing the rate of change of the dependent variable over time (the trend); t is the time variable, typically representing the time periods in the dataset (e.g., 1, 2, 3...); ϵ_t is the error term, representing the random fluctuations or noise in the data that are not explained by the trend. In this equation, β_0 represents the initial level of the dependent variable, and β_1 represents the slope or rate of change of the trend over time. By estimating the coefficients β_0 and β_1 , you can determine the starting point and the direction and magnitude of the trend.

Malmquist Productivity Index

The Malmquist productivity index, as proposed by Caves *et al.*, (1982), helps to describe multi-input, multi-output production without involving explicit price data and behavioral assumptions. It is a non-parametric methodology that uses data envelopment analysis (DEA) methods to construct a piece-wise linear production frontier for each country and year in the sample (Ajao, 2012). This methodology has been used extensively for measuring agricultural productivity, as it offers some advantages: a) does not require price information, b) does not assume that all countries are efficient, c) does not assume a behavioral objective function such as cost minimization or revenue/profit maximization, and d) it allows for TFP decomposition into

technical change, efficiency change and scale change (Coelli *et al.*, 2005).

Ajao (2012) reported that the output based Malmquist productivity index as a measure of productivity growth was introduced by Cave *et al.*, (1982). They specify the Malmquist productivity index as the geometric mean of these two indices:

$$M_o(x_t, y_t, x_{t+1}, y_{t+1}) = \left[\frac{d_o^t(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^t(x_t, y_t)} * \frac{d_o^{t+1}(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^{t+1}(x_t, y_t)} \right] \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where $d_o^t(x_t, y_t)$ is the output distance for year t, which is defined as the ratio of observed output to the maximum output, y producible with given technology and input vectors, x (Shephard, 1953). The superscript is the value of the output distance evaluated at input-output of year t+1 using technology of year t. Equation (1) can be decomposed into the following two components namely efficiency change index which measures the output-oriented shift in technology between two periods and the technical change between period t+1 and t. If the technical change is greater (or less) than one, then technological progress (or regress) exists. Here, EFFCH and TECHCH represented efficiency change and technological change respectively. Symbolically,

$$EFFCH = \frac{d_o^{t+1}(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^t(x_t, y_t)} \dots\dots\dots(2) \quad \text{and}$$

$$TECHCH = \left[\frac{d_o^t(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^{t+1}(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})} X \frac{d_o^t(x_t, y_t)}{d_o^{t+1}(x_t, y_t)} \right]^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

There exist several methods of estimating the distance functions which makes up the Malmquist TFP index. The most popular and widely adopted in recent time has been the DEA like linear programming (LP) methods suggested by Fare *et al.*, (1994) and its parametric equivalent – stochastic frontier method were adopted in this study.

Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)

The ARDL-Cointegration estimation technique was utilized in this study to analyze the long-term relationship between variables through ARDL model; it is used to establish the existence of a cointegration relationship among economic model variables in the model. Cointegration often refers to the fact that two or more series share a stochastic trend, it focuses on whether there is a

long-term linear relationship between two or more-time series. The model incorporates error correction mechanisms, all owing for the examination of short-term dynamics and adjustment processes that bring variables back to their long-term equilibrium (Pesaran *et al.*, 2001; Ewetan *et al.*, 2020, Iyke and Ho 2020).

An ARDL Bounds test for cointegration proposed by Pesaran and Shin (1999) was applied in this study in order to ascertain the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables under consideration in model. For ARDL variables

$$TFP = f(GAE, AGDP, EXR, GCF, INF, PS, AL, FA) \dots\dots\dots 4$$

The econometric form of equation 1 is as follows:

$$Y_t (TFP_t) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GAE_t + \alpha_2 AGDP_t + \alpha_3 EXR_t + \alpha_4 GCF_t + \alpha_5 INF_t + \alpha_6 PS_t + \alpha_7 AL_t + \alpha_8 FA_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots 5$$

Where Y_t = Dependent variable, α_0 = Intercept; $\alpha_1 - \alpha_{10}$ = coefficients of the independent variables; TFP = Agricultural Total Factor Productivity; GAE = Government Agricultural Expenditure (Percentage of GDP); AGDP = Agricultural Gross Domestic Product (Proxy for agricultural growth); EXR = Exchange rate; GCF = Gross Capital Formation; INF = Inflation Rate; PS = Political Stability; AL = Agricultural Labour; FA = Food Aid; μ_t = Stochastic Error Term.

The log form is specified as follows:

$$\Delta LTFP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \Delta LGAE_t + \alpha_2 \Delta LAGDP_t + \alpha_3 \Delta LEXR_t + \alpha_4 \Delta LGCF_t + \alpha_5 \Delta LINF_t + \alpha_6 \Delta LPS_t + \alpha_7 \Delta LAL_t + \alpha_8 \Delta LFA_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots 6$$

The variables were estimated in their log forms so as to ensure that the best possible sets of estimates are gotten from the analysis.

Stationarity Test: Panel Unit Root Tests

A preliminary test of stationarity aimed at determining whether the variables in their time series form have dependable means and variances will be done using panel unit root tests (like the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF), the Levin-Lin-Chu test, the Im-Pesaran-Shin test and the Hadri LM test) to test for order of stationarity of the series. Also, the presence of long run relationship among the variables was tested using Engle-granger cointegration method which specifies that

though all the series may not be stationary at first difference, if their residual is stationary at levels $I(0)$, there can still be a long run relationship among the series, and the test of long run relationship among the series is called cointegration.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stationarity Test for First Stage – Variables for TFP Decomposition and Analysis

The summary statistics were utilized to test for unit root in the variables, to avoid spurious or nonsensical regression. The analysis primarily focused on the Levin, Lin & Chu test, while also referencing the Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat test (Table 1). The Eviews results also included the ADF - Fisher Chi-square and the PP - Fisher Chi-square tests, which confirmed the stationary status observed with the Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat test across all variables. Specifically, all variables in the model exhibit stationarity at first difference at the 1% level of significance. At levels, only Fertilizer Consumption is stationary across all levels. Rural Population and Agricultural Land Area (ALA) are stationary at 5% and 10% level of significance respectively. The remaining variables demonstrate nonstationarity across all significance levels at the original levels. This suggests that only the variable of Fertilizer Consumption in the model exhibit mean-reversion at the original levels. Upon differencing the variables once, all variables display mean-reversion, with no unit roots at the 1% level of significance, confirming the rejection of the null hypothesis of the presence of unit root.

Table 1: Result of Unit Root Tests

VARIABLES	AT LEVELS	AT FIRST	ORDER OF INTEGRATION
	DIFFERENCE		
	SUMMARY	SUMMARY	
Value of Agricultural Production (VAGP)	5.8826	-16.2414***	I(1)
Tractorization	5.8031	-14.2966***	
	-1.01927	-21.8668***	I(1)
	-0.17802	-18.2747***	
Rural Population	-1.86115**	-15.9674***	I(1)
	2.68262	-14.7514***	
Agricultural Land Area (ALA)	-1.38812*	-16.4824***	I(1)
	1.26984	-16.2410***	
Fertilizer Consumption (FC)	-2.17972**	-20.4890***	I(1)
	-1.28957*	-18.4483***	

Note: Levels of significance are represented thus: 1% (***), 5% (**), 10% (*). First difference values with ** are significant at all levels.

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

Decomposition of TFP of ECOWAS member states agricultural sector into its major components using DEA Malmquist indices.

Agricultural TFP Growth and Performance of ECOWAS member states: 1980 – 2022

The results of the agricultural total factor productivity growth and performance of ECOWAS member states as shown in Table 2 revealed that all the 12 ECOWAS member states studied had negative TFP growth, ranging from -20.74 percent (Togo) to - 41.15 percent (Gambia).

ECOWAS sub-region as a whole experienced a 33.48 percent decline in productivity. Given country by country case, Benin witnessed a negative 34.87 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP), while Burkina Faso witnessed a negative 38.53 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period. The findings also indicated that Cote d'Ivoire witnessed a negative 40.21 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP), and Gambia witnessed a negative 41.15 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period. In the case of Ghana, the country witnessed a negative 37.49 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP), while Guinea Bissau witnessed a negative 33.7 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period. Mali, as a country also witnessed a negative 33.82 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP), Niger also witnessed a negative 30.27 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period. Equally, Nigeria witnessed a negative 30.59 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP), while Senegal also witnessed a negative 28.38 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period. The findings also revealed that Sierra Leone witnessed a negative 23.95 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period. Togo also witnessed a negative 20.74 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period. ECOWAS as a sub-region witnessed a negative 33.48 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period.

From the results above, there is a technological regression in ECOWAS agriculture as revealed by the consistently low values of Technological Change (TECHCH), suggesting the need for policies to promote technological adoption and innovation in ECOWAS agriculture. The agricultural sector of ECOWAS is yet experiencing efficiency stagnation as the values of efficiency change (EFFCH) is close to 1 indicate that efficiency levels are not improving significantly. Hence, there is a need for better resource allocation and management practices in the agricultural sector of the various ECOWAS member states.

Figure 1: Graph of the Trend of the Total Factor Productivity in ECOWAS 1980 – 2022)

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

Table 2: Summary of ECOWAS Member States’ Results of TFP Decomposition from Traditional Malmquist DEA Method Showing TFP Growth and Performance

COUNTRY	EFFCH	TECHCH	TFPCH	TFPCH GROWTH	TFPCH GROWTH (%)
Benin	1.0025	0.6460	0.6513	- 0.3487	- 34.87
Burkina Faso	1.0029	0.6114	0.6147	- 0.3853	- 38.53
Cote D’Ivoire	1.0030	0.5968	0.5979	- 0.4021	- 40.21
Gambia	0.9957	0.5950	0.5885	- 0.4115	- 41.15
Ghana	0.9974	0.6281	0.6251	- 0.3749	- 37.49
Guinea Bissau	0.9959	0.6670	0.6630	- 0.337	- 33.7
Mali	0.9975	0.6682	0.6618	-0.3382	- 33.82
Niger	0.9935	0.7044	0.6973	- 0.3027	- 30.27
Nigeria	0.9986	0.7001	0.6941	- 0.3059	- 30.59
Senegal	1.0002	0.7193	0.7162	- 0.2838	- 28.38
Sierra Leone	1.0048	0.7594	0.7605	- 0.2395	- 23.95
Togo	1.0128	0.7791	0.7926	- 0.2074	- 20.74
ECOWAS	0.9994	0.6690	0.6652	- 0.3348	- 33.48

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

The Trend Analysis of Agricultural GDP (% of GDP) in ECOWAS

The graph of the trend of agricultural GDP for ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States) from 1980 to 2022 reveals that for most of the period from 1980 to around 2015, the agricultural GDP remained relatively stable, showing that agriculture has maintained a consistent share of the overall economy during the period. From 2015-2018, there appeared to be a small slight increase in agricultural GDP share from around 2015. There was a sharp and dramatic increase in agricultural GDP share from 2018 to 2022. This is incongruent to the study of Ekpo and Umoh (2012) that revealed that the contribution of agriculture to GDP, which was 63 percent in 1960, declined to 34 percent in 1988, not because the industrial sector increased its share but due to neglect of agriculture sector.

Figure 2: Graph of Agricultural GDP in ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Agricultural Labour Force Participation in ECOWAS

The trend of agricultural labour force participation in ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States) from 1980 to 2022 revealed fluctuations in the agricultural labour force participation has fluctuated over the entire 42-year period (1980 to 2022). This is not in agreement with Sanga and Sebege (2018) which revealed that the beginnings of a structural transformation process in some ECOWAS economies, especially Ghana, Nigeria and Senegal, and more or less Burkina Faso and Guinea. The positive effects of the mobility of labour factor, was at slow pace, from the agricultural sector to the industrial (manufacturing industry mainly) and services sectors.

Figure 3: Graph of Agricultural Labour Force in ECOWAS (1980 - 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Exchange Rate in ECOWAS

The trend of exchange rate for ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States) from 1980 to 2022 shows a clear and consistent upward trend in the exchange rate from 1980 to 2020, indicating a long-term depreciation of the local currency unit (LCU) against the US dollar. This agrees with (Awe and Olalere, 2019) where the exchange rate trend in ECOWAS countries has shown significant fluctuations and depreciation against the US dollar since the 1980s. This fluctuation has had mixed effects on economic growth, with short-term negative impacts but potentially positive long-term effects (Umoru and Hussaini, 2022).

Figure 4: Graph of Exchange Rate in ECOWAS (1980 - 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Food Aid in ECOWAS

The trend of food aid trends for ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States) from 1980 to 2022 shows that from 1980 to 1985, the food aid trends for ECOWAS started with moderate levels of food aid, and then a dramatic sudden rise around 1985. From 1985 to 1995, there was a sharp decline followed by fluctuations. From 1995 to 2010, there was a gradual decline with some fluctuations which presented downward trend on the overall. From 2010 to 2020, the food aid trends for ECOWAS showed a sudden and more consistent decline in food aid until 2020. This align with Me-Nsope and Staatz, (2013) and Khan, (2021), they found that food aid trends in Sub-Saharan Africa, including ECOWAS countries, showed a rapid expansion in the early 1980s, with a significant increase during the 1984-1985 crisis. However, from 1980 to 2009, there was a general trend towards greater per capita calorie supplies and diversification in food composition for most ECOWAS countries.

Figure 5: Graph of Food Aid in ECOWAS (1980 - 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Government Agricultural Expenditure in ECOWAS

The trend of government agricultural expenditure for ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022 shows that from 1980 to 1985, the trend of government agricultural expenditure for ECOWAS started with a sharp decline. From 1985 to 1995, there was a slow but steady increase. From 1995 to 2000, there was a dramatic sudden rise, followed by a quick drop and subsequent fluctuations. From 2000 to 2015, the period showed consistent growth in government agricultural expenditure for ECOWAS. From 2015 to 2018, the trend of government agricultural expenditure for ECOWAS

increased greatly, but it was followed by a slight decline. From 2018 to 2022, the trend of government agricultural expenditure for ECOWAS experienced a great rise until 2022. This is congruent with the research work of Kamenya *et al.*, (2022) where they examine government expenditure and its impact on economic growth and food security in ECOWAS countries. Studies show that public agricultural expenditure has increased since 2003, with some countries meeting the 10% target. This increase has positively impacted food accessibility and availability, with a 1% rise in expenditure associated with reduced undernourishment and improved dietary energy supply is in alignment with this study.

Figure 6: Graph of Government Agricultural Expenditure in ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Gross Capital Formation in ECOWAS

The trend of gross capital formation for ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022 shows that from 1980-1985, the trend of gross capital formation for ECOWAS showed sharp decline. There was relatively stable period, with slight increase from 1985 to 1995. There was sharp decline in the gross capital formation from 1995 to 2000. There were fluctuations in the trend of gross capital formation from 2000 to 2010. The trend of gross capital formation recorded rapid increase from 2010 to 2015. From 2015 to 2022, the trend of gross capital formation continued as a strong upward trend. But on the overall, ECOWAS experienced a U-shaped trend in gross capital formation, with a significant recovery and growth in the last decade. This agreed with Ndiaye and Korsu (2016) who observed that growth in most ECOWAS countries from 1980-2012 was driven by factor accumulation rather than productivity, with capital contribution being positive in most countries

except Côte d'Ivoire and Nigeria. These findings suggest a complex interplay of factors influencing economic growth and capital formation trends in the ECOWAS region.

Figure 7: Graph of Gross Capital Formation in ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Inflation in ECOWAS

The trend of inflation for ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022 shows that from 1980 to 1995, ECOWAS experienced extremely high and volatile inflation rates. From 1995 to 2005, the trend of inflation for ECOWAS was a sharp decline in inflation rates, followed by a relatively stable period until about 2005. From around 2005 to 2015, inflation rates were generally low and stable. From 2015 to 2022, there was a noticeable upward trend in inflation from about 2015, with a sharp increase until 2022. This is consistent with (Otoakhia, 2022; Mahawiya *et al.*, 2020). The ECOWAS region has experienced varying inflation trends since 1980. From 1980 to 1995, inflation rates were extremely high and volatile. A sharp decline followed from 1995 to 2005, with rates remaining relatively stable until 2005. From 2005 to 2015, inflation rates were generally low and stable, but an upward trend emerged from 2015 onwards.

Figure 8: Graph of Inflation in ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

Stationarity Test for the Second Stage – Variables for Estimating the Effect of Government Agricultural Expenditure, and its Determinants on ECOWAS Agricultural TFP growth

The summary statistics were utilized to test for unit root in the variables, to avoid spurious regression. The analysis primarily focused on the Levin, Lin & Chu test, while also referencing the Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat test (Table 3). The results also included the ADF - Fisher Chi-square and the PP - Fisher Chi-square tests, which confirmed the stationary status observed with the Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat test across all variables. Specifically, all variables in the model exhibit stationarity at first difference at the 5% level of significance. At levels, only Agriculture Total Factor Productivity (TFPCH), Agricultural Gross Domestic Product (AGDP), Inflation (INFLA), and Food Aid (FOOD-AID) are stationary across all levels. Agricultural Labour (ALFP) is stationary only at the 10% level of significance. The remaining variables demonstrate nonstationarity across all significance levels at the original levels. This suggests that only the variables of Agriculture Total Factor Productivity (TFPCH), Agricultural Gross Domestic Product (AGDP), Inflation (INFLA), and Food Aid (FOOD-AID) in the model exhibit mean-reversion at the original levels. Upon differencing the variables once, all variables display mean-reversion, with no unit roots at the 5%, 1%, and 10% significance levels, confirming the rejection of the null hypothesis of the presence of unit root

Table 3: Result of Unit Root Tests

VARIABLES	AT LEVELS	AT FIRST	ORDER OF
		DIFFERENCE	INTEGRATION
	SUMMARY	SUMMARY	
Agriculture Total Factor	-14.6349**	-21.0493**	I(1)
Productivity (TFPCH)	-13.9629**	-22.4211**	
Government Agricultural Expenditure (GAE)	1.01845	-12.7692**	I(1)
Agricultural Gross Domestic Product (AGDP)	-3.55499**	-15.0405**	I(1)
Agricultural Labour (ALFP)	-1.34401*	-11.4370**	I(1)
Gross Capital Formation (GCF)	1.34716	-14.6240**	I(1)
Inflation (INFLA)	0.26840	-15.8141**	
Food Aid (FOOD-AID)	-7.41468**	-18.6140**	I(1)
Exchange Rate (EXCH-RATE)	-2.64276**	-17.1424**	I(1)
Political Stability (POL-STBLTY)	-3.77484**	-19.9694**	
	-0.00310	-5.79523**	I(1)
	-0.13310	-9.52161**	
	-0.53764	-7.96716**	I(1)
	0.23313	-9.58955**	

Note: Levels of significance are represented thus: 1% (***), 5% (**), 10% (*).

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

Cointegration analysis

The Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test was conducted on the variables to determine the short-run or long-run relationships between the variables in the panel analysis. Following the Johansen (1991) decision criteria, determining the presence of cointegration or a long-run relationship in panel data requires that the P-value of the Trace and Max-Eigen value statistics

exist at a level below the selected significance level. If the p-value is less than the specified level, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected. In this analysis, at the significance level of 0.05, the p-value (0.0003) for both the Trace and Max-Eigen value statistics, indicating at most 8 Cointegration Equations in the result, is lower than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis of the absence of eight cointegrating equations is rejected and the alternative hypothesis that there are at most eight cointegrating equations is accepted. This infers that the eight variables are perfectly cointegrated and display a long-run relationship, leading us to estimate a long-run ARDL model.

Table 4: The Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test Results

Unrestricted Co-Integration Rank Test (Trace and Maximum Eigen value)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Fisher Stat.* (from trace test)	Prob.	Fisher Star. * (from max-eigen test)	Prob.
None	347.3	0.0000	219.0	0.0000
At most 1	200.3	0.0000	95.29	0.0000
At most 2	114.5	0.0000	50.08	0.0014
At most 3	70.23	0.0000	30.14	0.1802
At most 4	45.20	0.0055	21.42	0.6141
At most 5	30.71	0.1623	19.35	0.7333
At most 6	23.67	0.4808	8.123	0.9990
At most 7	32.87	0.1069	19.41	0.7298
At most 8	54.81	0.0003	54.81	0.0003

***Probabilities are computed using asymptotic Chi- square distribution**

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

Investigating the effect of government agricultural expenditure and its determinants on agricultural productivity growth in ECOWAS using Panel ARDL analysis

Panel ARDL analysis was performed on the variables to investigate the effect of government agricultural expenditure on the productivity growth in ECOWAS member states. The coefficient estimates for both the short-run and long-run for the ECOWAS region were obtained and presented. Additionally, the impact relationship coefficients for each of the twelve member countries selected in the ECOWAS region in the data were calculated.

Panel ARDL Long-run Analysis

In Table 5, the long-run estimates indicate that there is a negative and significant relationship between Agricultural Total Factor Productivity (TFPCH) and Government Agricultural Expenditure (GAE). The panel ARDL coefficient between Agricultural Total Factor Productivity (TFPCH) and Government Agricultural Expenditure (GAE) is -0.0233, suggesting that a 1% increase in Government Agricultural Expenditure in the ECOWAS region will lead to a 2.3 % decrease in Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the region and vice versa. This is in line with Mose, (2014) in his study of long-run and short-run estimation of effect of government agricultural expenditure on economic growth and Diallo *et al.*, (2021) where agricultural expenditure was negative despite overall impacts of government spending on agricultural growth in Mali. It contradicts the study of Uremadu *et al.*, (2018), they finds a positive long-run relationship between government agricultural expenditure and agricultural output in Nigeria. Also, Ngepah and Sunge (2023) found that government agricultural expenditure has a significant positive effect on agricultural total factor productivity growth in South Africa.

Agricultural Gross Domestic Product (AGDP) and Agricultural Total Factor Productivity do not have any significant relationship in the ECOWAS region in the long run. In the long run in the ECOWAS region, Agricultural Labour (ALFP) and Agricultural Total Factor Productivity are significantly positively related, sharing a coefficient of 0.0190. This means that a 1% rise in Agricultural Labour in the ECOWAS region will lead to about a 1.9% corresponding rise in Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the region and vice versa. This is not in agreement with the work of Labintan and Ding (2012) who found that Agricultural labor has a negative effect on agricultural productivity in Benin.

Gross Capital Formation (GCF) and Agricultural Total Factor Productivity maintain a negative significant relationship with a coefficient of -0.0135. A 1% rise in Gross Capital Formation in the ECOWAS region leads to a 1.35% fall in Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the region and vice versa. It is inconsistent with Pasara and Garidzirai (2020) where gross capital formation (GCF) was found positive with economic growth.

Inflation (INFLA) and Agricultural Total Factor Productivity have a positive significant relationship in the long run in ECOWAS with a coefficient of 0.0021. This implies that a 1% rise in Inflation in the ECOWAS region leads to a 0.21% rise in Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the region and vice versa. This result does not agree with the research of Igbinoia and Igbinoia (2023) where inflation negatively impact economic growth. Food Aid (FOOD-AID) and

Agricultural Total Factor Productivity maintain a negative significant relationship with a coefficient of -0.00000074. A 1% rise in Food Aid to the ECOWAS region leads to a highly minimal fall (0.000074%) in Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the region and vice versa. This validate the work of Adan (2023) that found out that food aid has a negative impact on agricultural development in Bal'ad district. The Exchange Rate (EXCH-RATE) has an insignificant relationship with Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the ECOWAS region in the long run.

Political stability (POL-STBLTY) negatively and significantly impacts Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the long run in the ECOWAS region with a coefficient of -0.0069. A 1% rise in political stability within the ECOWAS region will lower Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the region by 0.69% and vice versa. This is consistent with Adebayo (2020) who found that political stability negatively and significantly impacts agricultural total factor productivity in the long run in the ECOWAS region, but it is inconsistent with the work of Osabohien *et al.*, (2021) where political stability positively impacts agricultural production and food security in the ECOWAS region.

Table 5: The Panel ARDL Long-run Model Results

Dependent Variable		Agricultural Total Factor Productivity (TFPCH)		
Independent Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	T-Statistics	Probability
GAE	-0.023326	0.001817	-12.83957	0.0000
AGDP	0.000223	0.000151	1.477786	0.1430
ALFP	0.019026	0.003386	5.618753	0.0000
GCF	-0.013478	0.000377	-35.73289	0.0000
INFLA	0.002089	0.000534	3.914339	0.0002
FOOD-AID	-7.38E-07	2.85E-07	-2.590508	0.0112
EXCH-RATE	-1.63E-05	1.74E-05	-0.933603	0.3531
POL-STBLTY	-0.006911	0.003182	-2.172157	0.0325

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

Panel ARDL Short-run Analysis

The short-term estimates from Table 6 demonstrated that at the 10% significance level, only Agricultural Gross Domestic Product and Gross Capital Formation have a significant effect on Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the ECOWAS region. This is in line with Karabou (2018) who also found that GCF is positive and significant with productivity. Furthermore, Agricultural Gross Domestic Product in the previous period, as well as in the last two periods, significantly affects Agricultural Total Factor Productivity, with positive and negative coefficients of 0.0542 and -0.0310 respectively. This suggests that a 1% increase in Agricultural Gross Domestic Product in the previous period leads to a 5.4% increase in current Agricultural Total Factor Productivity, while a 1% increase in Agricultural Gross Domestic Product two periods ago results in a 3.1% decrease in current Agricultural Total Factor Productivity in the ECOWAS region.

As expected, the coefficient of cointegration is significant with the expected negative sign (-1.4009). The negative sign of the cointegration equation indicates a backward movement toward long-run equilibrium from short-run shocks. When there is a deviation from the long-run equilibrium, the model strongly and rapidly corrects this deviation at the rate of 140.09% per period. The magnitude of adjustment being greater than 1 (1.4009) suggests that the adjustment back to long-run equilibrium is relatively fast, likely overcorrecting in the next period before stabilizing.

Table 6: The Panel ARDL Short-run Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob. *
COINTEQ01	-1.400943	0.459926	-3.046020	0.0031
D(TFPCH(-1))	0.246665	0.184893	1.334094	0.1856
D(GAE)	-0.200593	0.587996	-0.341148	0.7338
D(GAE(-1))	-0.715080	0.573610	-1.246633	0.2158
D(GAE(-2))	0.168203	0.484053	0.347488	0.7291
D(GAE(-3))	0.006959	0.415031	0.016768	0.9867
D(AGDP)	0.027313	0.025460	1.072759	0.2863
D(AGDP(-1))	0.054160	0.031929	1.696275	0.0934
D(AGDP(-2))	-0.030959	0.016098	-1.923141	0.0577
D(AGDP(-3))	-0.031392	0.022003	-1.426684	0.1572
D(ALFP)	0.088527	0.066262	1.336014	0.1850
D(ALFP(-1))	0.039639	0.087206	0.454540	0.6506
D(ALFP(-2))	-0.010272	0.063203	-0.162528	0.8713

D(ALFP(-3))	0.024009	0.094277	0.254660	0.7996
D(GCF)	0.019908	0.011376	1.750072	0.0836
D(GCF(-1))	-0.024753	0.021120	-1.171975	0.2444
D(GCF(-2))	-0.020969	0.038184	-0.549158	0.5843
D(GCF(-3))	0.041932	0.030744	1.363898	0.1761
D(INFLA)	-0.006672	0.006571	-1.015497	0.3127
D(INFLA(-1))	0.016684	0.022050	0.756654	0.4513
D(INFLA(-2))	-0.001338	0.011107	-0.120482	0.9044
D(INFLA(-3))	-0.020214	0.012881	-1.569238	0.1202
D(FOOD_AID)	1.17E-05	9.03E-06	1.300780	0.1967
D(FOOD_AID(-1))	3.87E-06	1.20E-05	0.322319	0.7480
D(FOOD_AID(-2))	-3.96E-06	9.13E-06	-0.433415	0.6658
D(FOOD_AID(-3))	-1.24E-05	8.70E-06	-1.430689	0.1561
D(EXCH_RATE)	0.056423	0.050263	1.122563	0.2647
D(EXCH_RATE(-1))	-0.183279	0.184320	-0.994348	0.3228
D(EXCH_RATE(-2))	0.200962	0.204059	0.984824	0.3274
D(EXCH_RATE(-3))	0.044224	0.040786	1.084303	0.2812
D(POL_STBLTY)	0.243713	0.421413	0.578323	0.5645
D(POL_STBLTY(1))	-0.395068	0.518892	-0.761368	0.4485
D(POL_STBLTY(2))	-0.058656	0.405092	-0.144796	0.8852
D(POL_STBLTY(3))	0.862206	0.897362	0.960823	0.3393
C	0.348772	0.187266	1.862442	0.0659

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

POST-ESTIMATION ANALYSIS

The Jarque-Bera test for normality has a probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$ which implies that the residuals of the model are normally distributed. The Heteroskedasticity test probability value of $0.0097 < 0.05$ implies that the variation of the residuals in the model are free from Heteroskedasticity. The Variance Inflation Factors test indicates that the variables in the model revolve around 1 and 5, indicating low and moderate multicollinearity in the model.

Table 7: The Post-Estimation Tests Results

Test	Statistics	Prob
Normality Test (JB)	1047377	0.000000
Heteroskedasticity Test	26.31385	0.0097
Multicollinearity(VIF) Test	Low and Moderate Multicollinearity	

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Within the reference period (1980 – 2022), across the ECOWAS countries, agricultural labour force participation (ALFP) has experienced serious fluctuations within the reference period; government agricultural expenditure (GAE) and gross capital formation (GCF) have both experienced rapid increases within the reference period; the exchange rate has consistently experienced an upward trend; food aid has consistently experienced a declining and downward movement; the inflation rate has recorded an upward trend. Hence, the need for ECOWAS member states to invest in agricultural investment and infrastructure development, and also work towards currency stability and inflation management. The ECOWAS region is experiencing a decline in agricultural productivity, with all the 12 member states studied experiencing negative Total Factor Productivity (TFP) growth. The region's TFP growth rate had declined by 33.48% due to technological regression and efficiency stagnation.

The results of the Panel ARDL revealed that, in the short-run both Agricultural Gross Domestic Product and Gross Capital Formation had a negatively significant effect on Agricultural Total Factor Productivity Growth. In the long-run, Government Agricultural Expenditure, Gross capital formation, Food aid and Political stability all had negatively significant effect on Agricultural Total Factor Productivity Growth in ECOWAS. Meanwhile Agricultural Labour Force Participation, Inflation Rate had a positive and significant effect on Agricultural Productivity Growth. Arising from the findings, this study recommends the following:

- Implementation of policies to maintain a competitive exchange rate and moderate inflation rates as well as encouraging political stability to reduce uncertainty thereby fostering a conducive environment which promote investment for agricultural growth.
- Integration of food aid with local capacity-building efforts to promote long-term food security and support agricultural infrastructure, inputs, and resilience, as well as developing solutions tailored to each country's unique agricultural sector challenges with readiness to ensuring continuity in agricultural policies in each country within the ECOWAS member states.
- Encourage regional integration and the need for member states to diversify in order to reduce dependence on few export commodities, enhance trade and resilience to external shocks, while promoting economic growth within the ECOWAS region.

6. REFERENCES

- Adan, M. A. (2023). The Effect of Food Aid on Agricultural Development in Bal'ad District. *American Journal of Agriculture*, 5(3), 1-23.
- African Union (2003). African Union declaration on agriculture and food security in Africa. Assembly/AU/Decl.4-11 (II).
- African Union (2014). Malabo declaration on accelerated agricultural growth and transformation for shared prosperity and improved livelihoods. Doc. Assembly/ African Union. (2014). Malabo declaration on accelerated agricultural growth and transformation for shared prosperity and improved livelihoods. Doc. Assembly/ AU/2(XXIII). Addis Ababa: African Union AU/2(XXIII).
- Ajao, O. A. (2012). Determinants of agricultural productivity growth in sub-sahara Africa: 1961-2003. *Tropical and Subtropical Agroecosystems*, 15 (3), 575-582.
- Awe, A. A., and Olalere, S. S. (2019). Exchange rate volatility and output growth in the economic community of West African States (ECOWAS)(1980-2015). *International Journal of Innovation and Resource Development*, 8(10), 12-23.
- Basudev, S. (2012). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nepal a minute analysis: revenue administration training center. Basic research, *Journal of business management*, 13, 37-40
- Caves, D. W., Christensen, L. R., and Diewert, W. E. (1982). The economic theory of index numbers and the measurement of input, output, and productivity. *Econometrica: journal of the Econometric Society*, 1393-1414.
- Coelli, T. J., Rao, D. S. P., O'Donnell, C. J., and Battese, G. E. (2005). An Introduction to Efficiency and Productivity Analysis. Springer, science & business media, second edition
- Cooksey, B. (2013). The Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) and agricultural policies in Tanzania: Going with or against the grain. *FAC Political Economy of Agricultural Policy in Africa (PEAPA) Working Paper*. www.futures-agriculture.org.

- Da Silva, C., and Mhlanga, N. (2009). Models for investment in the agricultural sector. In *FAO Expert Meeting on Foreign Investment in Developing Country Agriculture*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of Research Writing and Uses of Research Methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Diallo, M., Mouleye, I. S., Keita, G. H., Sy, B., Bamba, A., and Maïga, A. (2021). Analysis of the effects of public expenditure on agricultural growth in Mali. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 39(7), 42-50.
- ECOWAS Commission (2010). Regional agricultural policy.
- ECOWAS Statistical Bulletin (2011). www.ecowas.int. bidc-ebid.com/en/cedeaop.php.
- ECOWAS (2016). Annual Report (online: accessed 2 September 2019
<https://www.ecowas.int/documentation/ecowas-commission-annual-report/>)
- Edeh, C. E., Ogbodo, J. C., and Onyekwelu, U. L. (2020). Impact of Government Expenditure on Agriculture on Agricultural Sector Output in Nigeria (1981-2018). *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 4(10), 15-26.
- Ekerete, P. (2000). Assessment of agricultural contributions to total export marketing in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economic and Development Issues*, 1(2), 23-28.
- Ekpo, A. H., and Umoh, O. J. (2012). An overview of the Nigerian economic growth and development.
- Ernawati, E., Tajuddin, T., and Nur, S. (2021). Does government expenditure affect regional inclusive growth? An experience of implementing village fund policy in Indonesia. *Economies*, 9(4), 164.
- Ewetan, O. O., Matthew, O. A., Babajide, A. A., Osabohien, R., and Urhie, E. (2020). Fiscal federalism and economic development in Nigeria: An auto-regressive distributed lag approach. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 6(1), 1789370.

- Ewubare, D. B., and Eyitope, J. A. (2015). The effects of public expenditure on agricultural production output in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 3(11), 7-23.
- Färe, R., Grosskopf, S., Norris, M. and Zhang, Z. (1994), Productivity growth, technical progress, and efficiency change in industrialized countries. *American Economic Review*, 84 (1), 66-83.
- Heisey, P. W., and Fuglie, K. O. (2018). Agricultural research investment and policy reform in high-income countries. (No. 1477-2018-5459).
- Ibe, R. C., and Olulu-Briggs, O. V. (2015). Any nexus between public health expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria. *Iiard international journal of banking and finance research*, 1(8), 3-11.
- IFPRI/International Food Policy Research Institute (2013). Agricultural science and technology indicators (ASTI) database. Available online: <http://www.asti.cgiar.org/data/>.
- Iganiga, B. O., and Unemhilin, D. O. (2011). The impact of federal government agricultural expenditure on agricultural output in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics*, 2(2), 81-88.
- Ihugba, O. A. Chinedu, N. and Njoku A.C (2013). An assessment of Nigeria expenditure on the agricultural sector: Its relationship with agricultural output. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 5(5), 177-186.
- Igbinovia, E. L., and Igbinovia, I. M. (2023). Financial liberalization and economic growth in the ECOWAS Sub-Region. *Journal of Enterprise and Development (JED)*, 5 (2), 219-237.
- Itodo, A. I., Apeh, S., and Adeshina, S. (2012). Government expenditure on agricultural sector and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 8(4), 62-67.
- Iyke, B. N., and Ho, S. Y. (2020). The effects of transitory and permanent inflation uncertainty on investment in Ghana. *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 53(1), 195-217.
- Josephson, A. L., Ricker-Gilbert, J., and Florax, R. J. (2014). How does population density influence agricultural intensification and productivity? Evidence from Ethiopia. *Food Policy*, 48,142-152.

- Kalibata, A. (2010). Agricultural aid to Africa is living aid. Available on the internet at <http://blog.bread.org/2010/10/listen-to-these-african-voices-as-our-governments-take->
- Kamenya, M. A., Hendriks, S. L., Gandidzanwa, C., Ulimwengu, J., and Odjo, S. (2022). Public Agriculture Investment and Food Security in ECOWAS. *Food Policy*, 113, 102349.
- Karabou, F. E. (2018). Agricultural productivity in Ecowas region: does governance matter? *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, (6) 9, 246- 270.
- Khan, B. (2021). Food Security Index for Economic Community of West-African States (ECOWAS). *Journal of Advanced Research in Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 2(1),47-56. Kimenyi,
- M. S., Routman, B., Westbury, A., Omiti, J., and Akande, T. (2013). CAADP at 10: progress towards agricultural prosperity. *The Brookings Institution: Washington, DC, USA*.
- Labintan, A. C., and Ding, S. (2012). An assessment of agricultural productivity and major driving factors in the republic of Benin. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 5(4), 468-474.
- Lawal, W. A. (2011). An analysis of government spending on agricultural sector and its contribution to GDP in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(20).
- Lencucha, R., Nicole, E. P., Appau, A., Thow, A. M., and Drope, J. (2020). Government Policy and Agricultural Production: A Scoping Review to Inform Research and Policy on Healthy Agricultural Commodities. *Globalization and Health* 16, 1–15.
- Leonardo, M. (2011). The quality of public expenditure and its influence on economic growth: evidences from the state of rio grande do Sul (RS). Washington D.C
- Mahawiya, S., Haim, A., and EricFosu, O. A. (2020). Insearch of inflation limits for financial sector development in ECOWAS and SADC regions: A panel smooth transition analysis. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 8(1), 1722306.

- Matthew, A., and Mordecai, B. D. (2016). The impact of public agricultural expenditure on agricultural output in Nigeria (1981-2014). *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 11(2), 1-10.
- Mendelsohn R., and Wang, J. (2017). The impact of climate on farm inputs in developing countries agriculture. *Atmosfera* 30, 77–8
- Me-Nsope, N. M., and Staatz, J. M. (2013). Trends in per capita food availability in West Africa, 1980-2009.
- Mogues, T., Morris, M., Freinkman, L., Adubi, A., and Ehui, S. (2012a). Agricultural public spending in Nigeria. In *Public Expenditures for Agricultural and Rural Development in Africa* (pp. 68-108). Routledge.
- Mogues, T., Yu, B., Fan, S., and McBride, L. (2012b). The impacts of public investment in and for agriculture: Synthesis of the existing evidence.
- Mose, N. G. (2014). *Effect of government expenditure on economic growth in East Africa: A disaggregated mode* (Doctoral dissertation, Egerton University).
- Ndiaye, M. B. O., and Korsu, R. D. (2016). Growth accounting in ECOWAS countries: A panel unit root and cointegration approach. *Accelerated economic growth in West Africa*, 19-35.
- NEPAD (2014). New Partnership for Africa's Development. About CAADP. Available online at <https://www.d-caadp.net/about-caadp.php>.
- Ngepah, N., and Sunge, R. (2023). Agricultural expenditure and agricultural total factor productivity growth in South Africa. *AIMS Agriculture and Food*, 8 (2), 637-661.
- OECD (2014). Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. *OECD Factbook, Economic, Environmental, and Social Statistics*. Oecd.
- Oguntade, E.A (2014). Food losses in cassava and maize value chain in Nigeria. Analysis and recommendations for reduction strategies. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit(GIZ), Bonn, Germany.
- Olawumi, O. R., and Oyewole, A. O. (2018). Public Expenditure on Agriculture and output growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 7(4), 60-68.

- Otoakhia, E. I. (2022). Inflation and its uncertainty in Some ECOWAS member states: Transfer Entropy Approach. *Cent. Bank Niger. Journal of Application. Statistics*, 12, 87-124.
- Osabohien, R., Olurinola, I. O., Matthew, O. A., and Igharo, A. E. (2021). Enabling environment and agriculture in ECOWAS; Implications for food security. *WSEAS Trans. Environ. Dev*, 17, 38-46
- Pasara, M. T., and Garidzirai, R. (2020). Causality effects among gross capital formation, unemployment and economic growth in South Africa. *Economies*, 8(2), 26.
- Pesaran M. H., and Shin Y. (1999). An Autoregressive Distributed-Lag Modelling Approach to Cointegration Analysis. In: Strom, S., Holly, A., Diamond, P. (Eds.), *Centennial Volume of Rangar Frisch*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., and Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of applied econometrics*, 16(3), 289-326.
- Sanga, D., and Sebego, M. (2018). Structural Transformation of Economies of the Economic Community of West African States: An Empirical Analysis. *Development*, 43(1).
- Shephard, R. W. (1953). Cost and production functions princeton university press. *Princeton, New Jersey*.
- Suleman, S. M., Zhijun, Y. and Qadeem, F. (2020). Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Agriculture Growth in Pakistan, An Error Correction Modeling Approach, *Researcher*, 12(1):6-15
- Umoru, D., and Hussaini, R. (2022). Exchange rate devaluation, interest rate volatility, and investment growth: ECOWAS evidence. *Sriwijaya International Journal of Dynamic Economics and Business*, 6(2), 211-226.
- Uremadu, S. O., Ariwa, F. O., and Uremadu, C. E. D. (2018). Impact of government agricultural expenditure on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. *Current Investigations in Agriculture and Current Research*, 5(3), 679-688.
- Van de Walle, D. (2003). Behavioral incidence analysis of public spending and social programs. *François Bourguignon and Luiz. A. Pereira da Silva, eds., The Impact of*

Economic Policies on Poverty and Income Distribution. Evaluation Techniques and Tools, 69-83.

Wagner, A. (1890). Finanzwissenschaft. 3rd Edition. Partly reprinted in Musgrave, R.A. & Peacock, A.F. (Eds). *The classic in the theory of public finance*. London: Macmillan.

World data (2023). World data. Info. <http://www.worlddata.info/trade-agreements/ecowas-west-Africa.php>. Retrieved 16 December, 2023